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Jurnal 2016-yil 28-sentyabrda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Matbuot va axborot agentligi tomonidan № 0843 raqami bilan qayta ro‘yxatdan o‘tgan. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi OAK tomonidan 2019-yil 30-yanvarda chop etilgan OAK rayosati qarorlari bilan tasdiqlangan ro‘yxatga ko‘ra 07.00.00 - “Tarix”, 09.00.00 - “Falsafa”, 10.00.00 - “Filologiya” ixtisosligi bo‘yicha; OAK Rayosatining 2023-yil 31-oktyabrdagi 345-son qarori bilan 12.00.00 – “Yuridik fanlar”, 13.00.00 – “Pedagogika”, 19.00.00 – “Psixologiya” ixtisosliklari bo‘yicha doktorlik dissertatsiyalari asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etish tavsiya etilgan ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan.

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“HUSNI-XULQ”NING TARIXIY-NAZARIY VA FALSAFIY TALQINI

Ne'matova Orzigul Axmedovna

O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

ИСТОРИКО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКАЯ И ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ «ХУСНИ- ХУЛКА»

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HISTORICAL-THEORETICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF «HUSNI-KHULK»

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada “Husni-xulq” atamasining mazmuni, mohiyati ochib berilgan. “Husni-xulq”ning tarixiy-nazariy, an’anaviy va zamonaviy, falsafiy talqini tarixiy-nazariy, ilmiy-falsafiy adabiyotlar asosida qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. “Husni-xulq” atamasi qadimgi sivilizatsiyalarda qanday ma’no-mazmuni anglatishini, aynan qanday so‘zlar bilan izohlanganligi keltirib o‘tilgan. Qadimgi Misr, Mesopotamiya, Qadimgi Hindiston, Xitoy, Yunoniston, Rim kabi turli qadimiy sivilizatsiyalarda o‘ziga xos mazmun va mohiyatni anglatganini va istilohda qanday atamalar bilan talqin etilganligi yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: “Husni-xulq”, go‘zallik, chiroy, axloq, fe‘l-atvor, mukammallik, uyg‘unlik, axloqiy qonun, burch, ma’naviy kamolot.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается значение и сущность термина «Хусни-хульк». На основе историко-теоретической и научно-философской литературы проведен сравнительный анализ историко-теоретической, традиционной и современной, философской интерпретации «Хусни-хулька». Упоминается значение термина «хусни-хульк» в древних цивилизациях и точные слова, используемые для его описания. В разных древних цивилизациях, таких как Древний Египет, Месопотамия, Древняя Индия, Китай, Греция и Рим, он имеет определенное значение и суть, а также то, какие термины используются для его толкования во время революции.

Ключевые слова: «Хусни-хульк», красота, красота, нравственность, характер, совершенство, гармония, нравственный закон, долг, духовная зрелость.

Abstract: This article reveals the meaning and essence of the term “Husni Khulk”. Based on the historical-theoretical and scientific-philosophical literature, a comparative analysis of the historical-theoretical, traditional and modern, philosophical interpretation of “Husni Khulk” is carried out. The meaning of the term “Husni Khulk” in ancient civilizations and the exact words used to describe it are mentioned. In different ancient civilizations such as Ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, Ancient India, China, Greece and Rome, it has a certain meaning and essence, as well as what terms are used to interpret it during the revolution.

Key words: “Husni-khulk”, beauty, beauty, morality, character, perfection, harmony, moral law, duty, spiritual maturity.

Kirish. “Husni-xulq” atamasi o‘zbek tilidagi ikki arabcha “husn” (go‘zallik, chiroy) va “xulq” (axloq, fe‘l-atvor)”[1:565] so‘zlarining birikmasidan tashkil topgan. Bu atama insonning chiroyli axloqiy fazilatlarini, yaxshi xulqi va odob-axloqining go‘zalligi ma‘nosida ishlatiladi. “Husni-xulq” (حُسْنُ الْخُلُقِ) – arabcha ibora bo‘lib, “odobli xulq” yoki “yaxshi xulq” degan ma‘noni anglatadi. Bu tushuncha islom an‘analari va falsafasida chuqur ildizlarga ega bo‘lib, uning talqini qo‘llanishiga ko‘ra istilohlarda turlicha ma‘nolarda ham qo‘llaniladi. “Husni-xulq” ko‘p qirrali tushuncha bo‘lib, diniy hamda dunyoviy ma‘nolarda ham ishlatiladigan universal atamadir. Ushbu atama asrlar davomida dolzarb bo‘lib kelgan, jamiyat va madaniyatdagi o‘zgarishlar bilan hamohang rivojlanishda davom etmoqda.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Ezgu xarakter va axloqni o‘zida mujassam etgan “Husni-xulq” tushunchasining tarixiy taraqqiyot jarayonida rivojlanib, sayqallanib Qadimgi Misr, Mesopotamiya, Qadimgi Hindiston, Xitoy, Yunoniston, Rim kabi turli qadimiy sivilizatsiyalarda o‘ziga xos mazmun va mohiyat kasb etgan va istilohda bir qancha atamalar bilan talqin etilgan. “Husni-xulq” atamasi islomiy adabiyotlarda va axloqshunoslikka oid asarlarda paydo bo‘lgan bo‘lsa-da lekin tarixan go‘zallik, axloq va xulq atvorni ifoda etishi orqali tarixan shakllangan.

Qadimgi Misrda fazilat va axloq tushunchasi haqiqat, adolat va ilohiy tartib ma‘budasi Maat tushunchasi bilan chambarchas bog‘liq edi. Maat haqiqat va muvozanat ideallarini o‘zida mujassam etgan Misrliklarning ilohiy ma‘budasi hisoblanadi. “Misrliklar jamiyatda va shaxs hayotida uyg‘unlikni saqlash uchun Maatning ko‘rsatmalariga va axloqiy tamoyillariga rioya qilish zarur deb hisoblashgan”[2:226]. “Marhumlar kitobi” kabi matnlarda yaxshi amallar va ezgu xulq-atvorning keyingi dunyoda muhim ekanligi qayd etilgan.

Qadimgi Misrda “Husni-xulq” atamasi ikki xil ma‘noda ishlatilgan (sababi *“husn”* – chiroy, go‘zallik, shakl shamoyil, “xulq” – inson fe‘l atvorining mukammalligi deb talqin etilgan. **Qadimgi Mesopotamiyaning** rivojlangan davlatlari hisoblangan, Shumer va Akkad madaniyatida ezigulik haqidagi fikrlar ham mavjud edi. Birgina

misol, “Xammurapining qonunlar kodeksida to‘g‘ri va adolatli deb hisoblangan ko‘plab qonunlar va xatti-harakatlar standartlari mavjud bo‘lib, unda insonning fe‘l-atvori ifodalab berilgan. Bu qonunlarda halollik, mas‘uliyat va ijtimoiy adolat eng muhim tamoyil sifatida ta‘kidlanadi”[3:54]. Xulqning yuksak namunasi sifatida, Shumer afsonalari va dostonlaridan, “Gilgamish”da, do‘stlik, sharaf va axloqiy tanlov kabi tushunchalar qadrlangan.

Muhokama. Vedalar va Upanishadlarda inson tabiati, olam va ma‘naviy yetuklik haqidagi ko‘plab falsafiy mulohazalar mavjud. Ular, shuningdek, jismoniy va ma‘naviy ma‘noda uyg‘unlik, muvozanat va go‘zallik haqidagi g‘oyalarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Hind falsafasida “sattva” (mehribonlik, poklik) tushunchasini insonning ichki go‘zalligining uyg‘unlashgan ideal bilan chambarchas bog‘langan”[4:29]. “Husni-xulq” atamasini ma‘naviyat va falsafa doirasidagi go‘zallik va estetika bilan bog‘liq tushuncha sifatida, “ruhning tabiati (atman) va o‘z-o‘zini bilish yo‘li nuqtai nazardan, go‘zallikni nafaqat jismoniy sifat, balki ichki uyg‘unlik, poklik va ma‘naviy kamolotning in‘ikosi sifatida talqin etilgan”[5]. Qadimgi Hindistonda fazilat tushunchasi falsafa va diniy ta‘limotlarida markaziy o‘rin egallaydi. Veda matnlari ham uning izohi Upanishadlar ham, dxarma – axloqiy qonun va burch haqida bayon etiladi. Dxarma hayotning individual va ijtimoiy tomonlarini, jumladan, yaxshi xulq-atvor, halollik va boshqalarga g‘amxo‘rlik qilishdan iborat hodisa hisoblanadi. Hind falsafiy maktablarida “Husni-xulq” tushunchasi Hind falsafasining *Chorvaka Lokayata, Sankhya, Nyaya va Vaisheshika* kabi turli falsafiy maktablari prizmasi orqali tahlil qilinganda, maktablarning har biri go‘zallik, tabiat va idrok haqida o‘ziga xos qarashlarni ifoda etadi.

Chorvaka yoki Lokayata materialistik dunyoqarashga ega falsafa bo‘lib, hissiy idrok va empirik tajribaga urg‘u beradi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, go‘zallik (husn) jismoniy his-tuyg‘ular orqali qadrlanadigan voqelik sifatida talqin etilgan. “Chorvakalar metafizik tushunchalarni inkor etib, haqiqiy voqelikni faqat kuzatish va boshdan kechirish orqali anglash mumkin”[6:36], deb ta‘kidlaydilar. Shunday qilib, ular go‘zallikni

birinchi navbatda jismoniy joziba va hissiyotlardan zavqlanish deb tushunishgan.

Sankxya dualistik qarashni ilgari surgan falsafiy maktab bo'lib, Purusha (ong) va Prakriti (tabiat) o'rtasida farqlanadi. Ushbu tizimda go'zallik tabiatdagi uyg'unlik va tartib bilan bog'lanadi. "Go'zallik (husn) Purusha va Prakriti o'rtasidagi muvozanatda namoyon bo'ladi"[7] degan qarashni ilgari surgan. Bu yerda estetik idrok tabiat qonunlari va ularning uyg'unligini anglash bilan bog'liq bo'lib, go'zallik inson ichki ma'naviy olamining ifodasi deb baholanadi.

Nyaya falsafasi mantiq va epistemologiya asosiga qurilgan. Bu yerda go'zallikka to'g'ri bilim va idrok nuqtai-nazaridan qaralgan. "Nyaya falsafasida ta'kidlashicha, go'zallik haqidagi bilimga ob'ektlarni to'g'ri idrok etish va tushunish kiradi. Go'zallikni mantiqiy tahlil qilish mumkin bo'lgan shakl, rang va mutanosiblik kabi toifalar orqali aniqlangan"[8:123]. Shu nuqtai nazardan husni-xulq estetik sifatlarni to'g'ri anglash bilan bog'liq hodisa deb hisoblangan.

Vaisheshika maktab vakillari "voqelikning atomistik xususiyatini tasniflaydi, aynan mana shu tasniflashda go'zallik ob'ektlarning sifatlari va munosabatlari orqali tahlil qilinadigan xususiyat sifatida qabul qilinadi"[9:217]. Vaisheshika dunyoni turli elementlardan iborat deb hisoblaydi va go'zallikni ularning kombinatsiyasi va o'zaro ta'siri natijasi sifatida talqin etadi. Demak, husni-xulq predmetlarning estetik qiymatini anglash orqali ularning sifatlarni o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Qadimgi Xitoy falsafasi inson xulq-atvorini va jamiyatdagi o'zaro munosabatlarni chuqur o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, "husni-xulq" tushunchasi turli falsafiy maktablar tomonidan o'ziga xos talqin qilingan. Ushbu tushuncha asosan Konfutsiychilik, Daosizm va Moizm kabi maktablar falsafiy ta'limotlarining muhokama markazi hisoblanhan. Konfutsiy ta'limoti va qarashlarida "husni-xulq", "asosan *"jen"*(仁), ya'ni mehr-oqibat, insonparvarlik tushunchasi bilan bog'liq tarzda ifodalangan. Konfutsiy fikricha, "husni-xulq"-insonparvarlik va adolat *"li"*(禮) qoidalariga amal qilishda namoyon bo'ladi"[10:116]. Har bir kishi jamiyatda o'zining ijtimoiy rolini tushunib, unga mos ravishda xulq-atvorni shakllantirishi, axloqli bo'lishi, nafaqat individual hayotning, balki, jamiyat barqarorligining ham asosi hisoblanadi. Qadimgi

Xitoy falsafasining yirik ta'limoti hisoblangan Daosizm "husni-xulq" konfutsiy ta'limotidan keskin farq qilgan. Insonning, tabiat bilan uyg'unlikda yashash bilan bog'liq hodisa hisoblangan. Daosizm asoschisi Lao Tsi "axloqiy qoidalariga qat'iy amal qilishni emas, balki, tabiiylik (自然,) va oddiylikni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Axloqning sun'iy ijtimoiy normalariga emas, balki "Dao" (道) yo'lga ergashish g'oyasi ilgari surilgan"[11:172]. Demak, "Husni-xulq"ni inson o'z qalbi bilan tabiat uyg'unligini anglab yetganda tabiiy ravishda hosil bo'ladigan holat sifatida baholagan.

NATIJALAR. Milet maktabi Qadimgi Yunonistonning falsafiy oqimlaridan biri bo'lib, eramizdan avvalgi VII–VI asrlarda faoliyat ko'rsatgan. Fales, Anaksimandr va Anaksimenlar ushbu maktabning asosiy vakillari hisoblanadi. Asosiy faoliyati tabiat falsafasi bilan bog'liq masalalar doirasida shug'ullanishgan. O'z e'tiborlarini olamning asosiy mohiyati (arxe) va tabiat qonunlariga qaratganlar. Ammo ular "husni-xulq" masalasiga bevosita chuqur e'tibor qaratmagan bo'lsalar-da, ularning dunyoqarashlari va falsafiy yondashuvlari axloqiy masalalarni o'rganishda keyingi maktablarga ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Milet maktabi vakillarining fikricha "Tabiat va insonning uyg'unligi inson tabiatning bir qismi ekanini va tabiat qonunlarini tushunish orqali, tabiatdagi barcha narsa bir asosdan arxe (asosiy element) kelib chiqqan. Bu birlik falsafasi axloqni ham insoniyatning umumiy mohiyati sifatida ko'rish uchun zamin yaratgan"[12:976]. Suqrot (mil.av. 470/469 – Afina – 399), Aflotun (mil.av. 428/427 – mil. av. 348/347) va Arastu (mil.av. 384/383, Stagira – mil.av. 322/321, Xalqida)ning "husni-xulq" haqidagi qarashlari qadimgi yunon falsafasining axloqiy masalalarga bag'ishlangan eng muhim asoslarini tashkil etadi. Ular insonning axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantirish, husni-xulqning mohiyati va maqsadini tahlil qilishda alohida yondashuvlarga ega bo'lib, o'z davri va keyingi asrlardagi axloqshunoslik taraqqiyotiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Suqrotning husni-xulq haqida asosiy e'tibori insonning axloqiy o'zini anglashiga qaratgan bo'lib, "u axloqni insonning ichki dunyosi va aqliy rivojlanishi bilan bog'lagan. "Husni-xulq" bilim bilan bog'liq. U "bilim – bu fazilat" degan fikrni ilgari surgan[13:1315]. Uning fikricha, inson axloqiy

jihtadan noto'g'ri xatti-harakat qilsa, bu uning bilimsizligidan kelib chiqadi.

Aflotunning husni-xulq haqidagi fikrlari asosan, axloqiy qarashlari idealizmga asoslangan. U husni-xulqni insonning ruhiyati va jamiyatdagi vazifalari bilan bog'lagan. Aflotun "inson ruhini uch qismga ajratgan: 1) aql (bilim olishga intilish), 2) jasorat (iroda va qat'iyat), 3) mayl (istak va xohishlar). "Husni-xulq" inson ruhining ushbu qismlari o'rtasidagi muvozanatni ta'minlash bilan yuzaga keladi. Aql yuqori o'rinda bo'lishi kerak, chunki u boshqa qismlarni boshqaradi"[14:44]. Aflotunga ko'ra, "husni-xulqning asosiy mezoni – adolatdir. Adolat nafaqat insonning ichki dunyosida, balki jamiyatda ham muhim o'rin tutadi. Husni-xulq adolatni saqlash va jamiyatdagi har bir shaxsning o'z vazifasini bajarishi orqali rivojlanadi"[15:45]. Aflotun "husni-xulq"ning to'rt asosiy fazilat komponentlarini (donolik, jasorat, me'yor va adolat) orqali tushuntirgan. Arastu axloq masalalariga amaliy va realistik nuqtai-nazaridan yondashgan. U "husni-xulq"ni insonning hayotdagi baxt-saodatga (eudaimonia) erishish uchun muhim vosita sifatida ko'rgan. Arastuning "husni-xulq haqidagi eng mashhur nazariyasi "o'rta yo'l" konsepsiyasi bo'lib, u axloqiy fazilatlarini haddan tashqari ko'p yoki kam bo'lmagan holat sifatida talqin qilgan"[16:1392]. Masalan, jasorat fazilat bo'lib, u qo'rqqoqlik va jasurlikning o'rtasida joylashgan. Arastu fazilatlarini ikki guruhini ajratgan: 1) Intellektual fazilatlar (bilim va tafakkurga asoslangan); 2) Axloqiy fazilatlar (amaliyot va odat orqali shakllanadigan). Axloqiy fazilatlar odat va tarbiya orqali shakllanadi. Shu sababli, husni-xulq insonning kundalik hayotdagi amaliy tajribasiga bog'liq.

Sitseron (e. avv. 106–43-yillar) Rim falsafasining yirik namoyandasi bo'lib, u axloqiy masalalarni davlat boshqaruvi va ijtimoiy munosabatlar bilan bog'lagan. Husni-xulq insonning o'z fazilatlarini va ijtimoiy majburiyatlarini to'g'ri anglashida namoyon bo'ladi. Sitseron adolat, mardlik, donolik va ehtiyotkorlikni asosiy axloqiy fazilatlar sifatida ko'rsatgan. Sitseron jamiyatdagi husni-xulqni saqlash uchun qonun va axloqiy me'yorlarning birligiga ishonadi. Yaxshi davlat boshqaruvi fuqarolarning axloqiy xulq-atvorini mustahkamlaydi.

Xulosa. Husni-xulqning tarixiy-nazariy va falsafiy talqini insoniyat taraqqiyotining turli bosqichlarida turli xalqlar falsafiy qarashlarida

ifodalanib kelgan. Qadimgi tsivilizatsiyalar Misr, Mesopotomiya, Hindiston, Xitoy, Yunoniston va Rimda "Husni-xulq", axloqiy me'yorlar va insoniylik tamoyillarini o'ziga xos falsafiy qarashlar orqali izohlagan. Husni-xulq qadimgi tsivilizatsiyalar falsafasida insonning jamiyatdagi o'rni, o'zini boshqarish va tabiat bilan uyg'un yashash masalalari orqali talqin qilingan. Bu falsafiy qarashlar hozirgi zamonaviy axloqiy tushunchalarga asos bo'lib xizmat qilgan va insoniyat ma'naviy taraqqiyotini yuksaltirgan. Har bir tsivilizatsiya husni-xulqni o'ziga xos madaniy, diniy va falsafiy qarashlar bilan izohlagan.

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